

THE FEELING OF TOLERANCE IN THE WORLD VIEW OF EDUCATED YOUTH

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Annotation: The spiritual world of a person determines his tolerance, attitude towards another person with appreciation and respect for his rights. All these qualities should be inculcated from a younger age, since at this age good acquired knowledge remains forever. Tolerance is an important factor for the stable development of the state and society.

Key words: spirituality, people, personality, upbringing, tolerance, freedom.

Аннотация: Духовный мир человека определяет его толерантность, отношение к другому человеку с признательностью и уважением к его правам. Все эти качества следует прививать с юных лет, так как в этом возрасте хорошие приобретенные знания остаются навсегда. Толерантность является важным фактором стабильного развития государства и общества.

Ключевые слова: духовность, народ, личность, воспитание, толерантность, свобода.

Each person, learning and studying the world, seeks to streamline and create the concept of a model of the real world surrounding him. Those who are highly qualified specialists in any field of science are in a hurry to conduct experiments, creating their own holistic systems of ideas about the general phenomena and patterns of reality [1].

Today, the human heart and mind are becoming more intense than ever and ideological processes are becoming more important in post-independence countries. After independence, one of the most important tasks of our time remains the education of a new generation of thinkers who will adapt to these processes.

In connection with the restoration of our national heritage and values, the growing awareness of national identity, significant positive changes are taking place in the minds of people. Changes in the spiritual and educational processes have taken root in the hearts and minds of our people, cultivating in them confidence in the future, in their strengths, in their capabilities, in love for the Motherland, in freedom. Only a spiritually free nation can make great progress in every field through deep and complete reflection. It is known that the first condition for high spirituality is freedom. Indeed, the concept of "citizen" and the concept of "freedom" are synchronized and synonymous.

In a free person of a free country, at the level of a wide range of possibilities, spiritual renewal can occur, inherent in the mentality of their nation, independent thinking can be formed.

Tomorrow the younger generation will become a reliable rear, the main economic, industrial, creative and intellectual force of our people.

To do this, the level of their worldview and thinking must meet the high requirements of the modern world, which will determine the future development of the country, the position of our people in the world community.

Therefore, today the goal is to consider education as a social phenomenon, which is carried out in the interests of society and in accordance with its level of development.

N.G. Chernyshevsky wrote: "There is no need to prove that education is the greatest blessing for a person. Without education people are rude and poor and unhappy".

Education plays an important role in a person's life, because with its help he can reach incredible heights. An educated and professional person will always be in demand in the labor market. With the help of education, a person can expand his horizons, learn and study the culture and traditions of different peoples, read scientific journalism and world literature, listen to classical music, visit exhibitions and museums, which are sources of knowledge. Studying the unfamiliar, a person discovers something new and begins to look at the world with different eyes.

It is known that a person has an inner and outer world. The outside world includes his height, appearance, clothes, behavior, and so on. His inner world includes his feelings, goals in life, his thoughts, his dreams, his aspirations. This inner world of man is spirituality. While food gives a person strength, spirituality gives him spiritual nourishment and strength. Spirituality is associated with enlightenment and culture. Spirituality is born through constant reading and learning.

It should be noted that the richer the spirituality, the richer the society and the nation. A spiritual person knows exactly what the purpose of life is, finds a way to live a meaningful life, acquires a culture of conversion, approaches every issue from the point of view of honesty, justice and tolerance. The most important component of culture is language, which serves as the basis for the transfer of experience and knowledge to future generations [2]. Inseparable concepts of a single whole are language and culture, in the aggregate of which spirituality creates.

In a society with a mature spirituality, the concept of tolerance is the face, pride and prestige of the nation. A person throughout his life learns to be tolerant of the people around him, as well as animals, nature. People learn to show respect and understanding, to accept others as they are. All these qualities should be inculcated from a younger age, since at this age good acquired knowledge remains forever. The spiritual world of a person determines his tolerance, attitude towards another person with appreciation and respect for his rights [3].

In recent years, inter-confessional conflicts associated with the infringement of religious minorities have been exacerbated in the world. In this regard, in Uzbekistan, issues related to human rights and freedoms have become one of the main programs of the new political course. Ignorance and religious intolerance are factors that contradict tolerance and society as a whole. On the territory of Uzbekistan, many nations and nationalities have long existed with their centuries-old cultural traditions, which did not prevent them from living side by side. The tolerant atmosphere has been preserved today throughout Uzbekistan. For centuries, Uzbekistan sacredly keeps and honors the centuries-old traditions of a tolerant nature. The policy of modern Uzbekistan is focused on interfaith dialogue, characterized by tolerance and peacefulness of its

citizens in relation to other faiths. Tolerance is an important factor for the stable development of the state and society as a whole [4].

The spiritual world of a person determines his tolerance, attitude towards another person with appreciation and respect for his rights. All these qualities should be inculcated from a younger age, since at this age good acquired knowledge remains forever. Tolerance is an important factor for the stable development of the state and society [5].

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